

Understanding Collatz conjecture

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Abstract

This paper is about understanding Collatz conjecture in hailstone numbers.

1 Understanding

Hailstone numbers(commonly referred in Collatz conjecture) is a sequence in following form[1]:

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} n/2 & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 3n + 1 & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Collatz conjecture is that these sequences always reach 1. In given statement of Hailstone numbers, assuming n is Odd or Even:

$$\begin{aligned} 3 \cdot \text{Odd} + 1 &= \text{Even} \\ \text{Even}/2 &= \text{Even or Odd} \\ \Rightarrow f(n) &= \text{Even}/2 \text{ or } (3 \cdot \text{Odd} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

The statement by Collatz conjecture is equivalent to:

Assuming $a_1 = k$ and $a_{n+1} = 3a_n + 1$,
 a_n could be formalized in sum of $2^x 3^y$ for $\forall k \in \mathbb{N}, \forall x \in \mathbb{Z}, \forall y \in \mathbb{Z}$.

This proposition is equivalent to:

For any given n , n could be formalized in sum of $2^x 3^y$ for $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \forall x \in \mathbb{Z}, \forall y \in \mathbb{Z}$.

And by the fact that multiplication of any ternary number with any binary number could be in \mathbb{N} , this is true.

2 Conclusion

Collatz conjecture is true.

References

- [1] Jeffrey C. Lagarias, editor. *The ultimate challenge. The $3x + 1$ problem*. Providence, RI: American Mathematical Society (AMS), 2010.

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